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'I DON'T UNDERSTAND WHAT KWH MEANS'

SIMULATE ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION DATA PROVISION TO HOUSEHOLDS

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ABSTRACT

Smart metering technology is currently being implemented in many European households, though at slower rate in the Netherlands. The technology offers the possibility to record and retrieve energy consumption data in real time. This may in turn influence household energy consumption behaviour. This paper presents the study on how inhabitants perceive energy consumption in relation to daily routines and activities. The study involved 16 participants from four households in The Netherlands. The findings demonstrated that the participants could not effectively equate the raw data consumption to be household behaviour at the entire household level, but were able to do so when the information was linked to certain appliances and routines. The paper describes the user study, results, and discusses recommendations on designing for products for energy consumption feedback and sustainable behaviour shaping in the home.

Keywords: design research; behaviour change; smart meter

SMART METERING TECHNOLOGY AND INTRODUCTORY PRODUCTS

Smart metering is able to track energy consumption in real-time. This promises mutual benefits to consumers and energy providers: consumers can monitor and optimize their energy consumption and suppliers have the information they need to balance supply and demand (Siemens Energy, 2011). Smart meters are expected to be installed in 80 percent of all European households by 2020 as follows from the energy policy adopted by the European Commission (Giglioli, 2010). While this goal does not seem likely in the Netherlands, given issues associated with trust and privacy, there has been an increase in voluntary

adoption of smart grids in recent years. Projects such as Power Matching city in Hoogkerk are considered as paving the way for smart grids in the Netherlands (Kok et al., 2011).

In spite of the fact that the infrastructure has not matured in the market, smart grids as a technological innovation provides an opportunity for new home applications; there are growing numbers of products that can help manage energy consumption data, including add-on conventional supply meters. Such products touch upon different aspects of smart metering: (a) measuring energy consumption at home; (b) giving feedback about usage to inhabitants; (c) sharing consumption data with others. For example, 'Wattson' (Figure 1 left) is a set of devices composed of a sensor clip, a transmitter and a display box. The energy pulse sensor clip measures the amount of flow on energy from the main line of the home circuit breaker, thus an indicator of the entire household energy consumption level. The Wattson the display shows the amount of electricity being consumed in real time with digits in kWh and an LED colour light on the box indicates the extent of consumption. A disadvantage of pulse sensors is the degree of accuracy of exact energy flow, but they do serve as rough indicators. 'Plugwise' (Figure 1 middle) is a plug adapter that measures energy consumption of the connected appliance and sends the data via wireless communication to a central device. Users can monitor the usage pattern with software on a computer. The display developed for the 'Energy Battle' study (Figure 1 right) emphasizes the social aspect of deploying the consumption data. Energy consumption data from each household is interpreted as an element of a game. Users play a game competing with their friends or neighbours to reduce energy consumption.

Figure 1. Example of applications manipulating energy consumption at home

These kinds of energy feedback devices have been shown to be somewhat effective in terms of influencing energy savings, but often only achieving short-term gains. (Van Dam, et al., 2010). However, there is little known about what specific requirements of feedback have impact on savings and how the provision of consumption information to individuals leads to saving energy (Pierce, 2010). Intille (2002 and 2003) suggest that feedback devices should help people to learn how to control the home environment by themselves rather than providing an automated environment. Therefore, product designers of home energy monitoring applications need to understand, not only what the data is about, but also what the data means to people, such that home occupants can act on the knowledge gained. This paper reports the research that explored how inhabitants make sense on energy consumption data. The following sections describe the background of study, research setting, deployed methods, and findings. Based on the study, the paper provides some preliminary design recommendations for home energy feedback devices linked to smart meters. The research was conducted as part of the Master course “Design Challenge” at Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands.

THE RESEARCH ON MEANING OF CONSUMPTION DATA

THE BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The research aimed to provide insights on designing a hand-held console, which delivers meaningful energy consumption information to fingertips of users. The design brief was presented by the design agency SHIFFT in The Netherlands, focusing on developing sustainable practices. The console communicates with smart meters monitoring energy consumption at home; electricity, water, and gas every 3 to 5 seconds. The design area covers both (1) technical development of a system that monitors, retrieves, and communicates the consumption data

within a home environment and (2) design of the interface of a product which persuades users to change their consumption behaviours toward a sustainable practice. The company was highly interested in a social aspect of deploying consumption data, sharing the data with other people in order to motivate and change people’s consumption behaviours. Considering the smart meter was not yet implemented in Dutch households, the project contractor also wished to get insights on how the new products can form a relationship between households and energy suppliers, beyond the designing of a product itself.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND SET-UP

The research investigated how the provision of the consumption data to people reshapes the ways they consume electricity in home. The goal of the research was to generate insights into technical and design related issues, including:

- (1) How home occupants understand energy feedback in relation to their activities;
- (2) How the data could motivate test participants to alter consumption behaviour;
- (3) How subjects would experience privacy issues in relation to sharing data with other households.

A user research was carried out with 16 participants from four households; two were Dutch family households and two were international student households. All were using traditional meters, and were not well aware about the smart metering technology. Three households had a direct contract with energy suppliers, and only one household had an inclusive energy contract, which had a fixed energy charge included in the monthly rent price.

RESEARCH METHODS

In order to investigate the questions above, we took the ‘practices approach’ to analyze the electricity consumption activities at home. Practices describe ways of doing - cooking, consuming, and working. They are the smallest units of human activities which consist of several elements, interconnected with behaviours, mental activities, things people use, and knowledge of how to use it (Reckwitz, 2002).

Practices are an inherent social aspect; these elements are structured in daily routines, but also evolve over time (Shove, 2003). We are particularly interested in the element of knowledge and mental activities, because presenting consumption information to consumers would educate how to use things and influence the image of consumption. For instance, Crosbie and Guy (2008) studied the influence of media promoting government policies and new products, which lead to strongly changing household lighting practices in the UK. Through this research we wanted to find out how behaviours, appliances, and knowledge regarding electricity consumption are embedded in people’s daily routines. Furthermore, we wanted to identify the opportunities of information that can influence energy consumption practice at home.

The research process was laid out to simulate the situation the situation when consumption data present to household. The research was processed in three steps (See Figure 2): (1) Collecting the electricity consumption data; (2) analyzing the gathered data; and (3) conducting interviews with participation with presenting the results.

Figure 2. The research procedure

To explain in detail, we collected three different types of data related to electricity consumption: the factual amount of consumption in kWh; the perceived amount of consumption by inhabitants; and the routine of daily activities being involved in consuming electricity. The data collecting was processed in the course of four days including weekends. We asked one participant per household to manually read the electronic meter every two hours while the participants were awake. This monitored the total electricity consumption of

households. We also collected the individual’s daily electricity consumption routine by asking them to fill in workbooks (Figure 2). In the workbooks, all individuals were asked to fill in their daily routine and activities involved in consuming electricity for four days, combined with the relative amount of electricity they thought they consumed by performing their routine. This intended to see the perceived amount of electricity consumption and compare this with actual usage. To avoid any interference by knowing the actual usage data, the people who monitored a meter did not fill in the workbook. After collecting the data, we analyzed them in order to create a ‘sense’ on how the participants consume electricity at home (2). The analysis was based on individual routines, consumption patterns of each household and comparison with other households. This derived information intends to present back to participants (3). This aimed to probe the probable effects on users by being exposed to the information and to get insights on how private users consider the information on their consumption.

FINDINGS FROM THE CONSUMPTION DATA

This section describes the insights from the collected data in three levels: individual consumption, consumption pattern of households, and comparison with more than two households.

Firstly, from the individual routines, six common activities were derived. They are: working, entertainment, cooking, cleaning/ washing, sleeping, and absence. These activities are laid on the graphs of actual consumption described in kWh (Figure 3).

Figure 3. A daily routine of one participant (activities are analysed)

Accordingly, we could understand how each activity contributes to the total amount of consumption in a day. We found certain individual activities take significant proportion in total consumption of a household in a day. For example, figure 3 shows one participants' report with a high consumption in the night because of using an electric heater (See (A) in Figure 3). Secondly, by aggregating the diaries of house members, we uncovered consumption patterns, which continue over days. For instance, household A has a peak of 4-6 kWh in consumption occurred during cooking and this repeated over several days (see (B) in Figure 4). This indicates that this activity possibly represents a critical activity in the consumption of electricity.

Lastly, it can be seen that the patterns differ a lot between the different households (See Figure 4); household A uses electricity mainly during the day and almost nothing at night whereas household C uses the most electricity during the night and almost nothing during the daytimes. Household C consumes a relatively higher amount of energy during sleeping and absence compared to the graph of household A. From the analysis, we learned that the collected data enables to provide knowledge on consumption both specifics breakdowns and overview patterns.

The results were presented to the participants in a follow-up interview to understand what they could learn and how they react to this information.

FOLLOW-UP INTERVIEW

In the follow-up interview, we presented the two different types information to the participants: first, the individual household's usage graph of four days with the involved activities annotated; second, a combined graph of the four households (the name of households were shown anonymously). By providing this information, we intentionally oriented the participants to reflect on their consumption behaviours with the information describe them. Also, by seeing not only their own usage patterns but also comparing what others spent on the same days, they were encouraged to feel how private this information is to them. The discovered insights are classified into four topics and are described in the following:

1. How the participants understood the usage information
 - They did not grasp the significance of units such as W and kWh.
 - By comparing activities they could understand relatively which activities consumed more or

Figure 4. The energy consumption graphs of households. Analysed activities are annotated.

less energy. E.g. It was perceived that one household wasting energy during the night because it was as same amount as watching TV

- They could often not explain why they consumed such amount of electricity. E.g. one house spent energy while all house members were absent, but they have no idea what happened.

2. Significant information to the participants

- They were interested in knowing what appliances mostly contribute to the amount of consumption in each type of activities.
- To get a reliable comparison between households, additional information such as types of household and number of family.
- They wanted clear and self-explanatory information that they could directly understand. They were not willing to analyze the given data consumed electricity.

3. Consumption data enable participants to value the amount of consumption

- With the given information, participants started judging their behaviours and spent energy; the relative value they earn from the each consumption is more important criteria than the actual amount itself. For example, one participant said that such amount of energy to keep light on during the night is worth to spend, because she feels afraid if the room is totally dark.

4. How private is the usage information

- As long as information is shared anonymously with other households, they do not consider this as an intrusion of their privacy.
- However, three participants said that specific data that indicates which appliances are being used and activity patterns should not be shared.
- Providing the usage information to a supplier was not seen as directly intruding their privacy, but they were concerned about the need for consent to access their information from third parties.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper described the study on how provision of energy consumption data can assist inhabitants to understand their usage behaviours and possibly reduce their consumption. We conclude that an information on breakdowns for consumption in the test households was valuable: first, it allowed the participants to identify relative amount of consumption by comparing them with those of other households; second, it was relatively easy for the participants to associate the data with their behaviours and appliances involved.

We recommend three ways of breaking down the data;

- Based on activities
An activity is an effective unit for breaking down a whole amount of consumption into comprehensive information. The meaningful units including cooking, washing and entertaining are common activities in households and therefore enable comparison with other households.
- Based on appliances
When the participants were confronted by odd figures in their consumption, they wanted to know which appliances actually contribute to this data. It includes details consumption information about appliances taking big portions of consumption like a refrigerator or damaged devices create abnormal consumption.
- Based on the time of absence or sleeping
It is found that the stand-by consumption could take a significant portion of the daily consumption pattern. When there is no actual activity at home, the existence of stand-by energy is easily revealed. It is necessary to put attention to these periods of time such as sleeping and absence.

DISCUSSIONS

As mentioned in the introduction, smart metering technology has not fully implemented to the market yet. There is lots of research on its potential value and effects but it is hard to 'see' how would it affect

to inhabitants. This research investigated how test households would experience and appreciate an unrealized technology by simulating the technology with an easy and simple setup. From the research we discovered a need to increase the resolution of retrieving consumption data, i.e. appliance level. An important area for further study is to investigate when the appropriate moment is to provide energy consumption data in relation people's every day.

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